

Non-holonomic Movement Primitives To Generalize Unicycle Trajectories

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Abstract—In this work, we propose a novel approach akin to Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs) for the purpose of unicycle path generalization. While drawing inspiration from DMPs, our approach differentiates by employing a nonlinear controller instead of the typical damped spring model found in DMPs. This modification allows us to address tasks involving non-holonomic constraints, thereby expanding the applicability of the approach.

Index Terms—Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs), Non-holonomic Robots, Trajectory Generalization

I. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs) present substantial benefits when it comes to encoding, generating, and adjusting intricate trajectories, paving the way for Learning from Demonstration (LfD). This approach finds application in a wide range of contexts, including autonomous navigation of nonholonomic robots. However, when dealing with nonholonomic robots, conventional DMPs may prove limiting.

Autonomous navigation of nonholonomic robots requires a deep understanding of nonholonomic constraints. Here lies a significant challenge as classical DMPs aren’t designed to respond to nonholonomic constraints. This challenge is notably demonstrated in the work described in [1], where the authors extend DMPs to tackle nonholonomic constraints in the context of robotic cutting from demonstration.

In our work, we address this challenge by integrating DMPs with a controller based on the Lyapunov principle, specifically designed for the unicycle model. Through this approach, we obtain the velocities needed to precisely control the orientation and position of the unicycle.

This strategy effectively generalizes trajectories, enabling mobile robots to learn complex movements with precision and versatility. This has broad implications for applications such as robot navigation in households and the field of Learning from Demonstration, unlocking new possibilities for robot utilization.

II. CONTEXT

A unicycle is a robot modeled as two parallel driven wheels that enable it to navigate within a plane. A distinctive characteristic of such robots is their embodiment of a nonholonomic mechanism, i.e. the absence of lateral slipping. The kinematic model of the unicycle in cartesian coordinates is:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= v \cos(\psi), \\ \dot{y} &= v \sin(\psi), \\ \dot{\psi} &= \omega. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Unicycle configuration in polar coordinates

With this clarification in mind, we can delineate our goal at the core of our challenge: to adapt a demonstrated trajectory to new starting and ending configurations while considering the inherent constraints.

Typically, problems of this nature are effectively addressed through a technique known as Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs). However, in this specific context, the application of DMPs faces limitations due to dynamic constraints.

DMPs, first introduced in reference [2], aim to minimize the distance between a demonstrated trajectory and the newly adjusted trajectory, while adhering to the updated endpoint constraints. DMPs achieve this minimization by adapting demonstrations in a particular manner, based on a specific choice of the Hilbert space norm [3]. They are formally defined through a set of nonlinear differential equations, as follows:

$$\tau^2 \ddot{v} = K(g - x) - Dv + (x_g - x_0)f(z), \quad (2)$$

$$\tau \dot{z} = -\alpha z. \quad (3)$$

With τ representing a temporal scaling factor, x denoting a discrete single DoF trajectory, and x_g and x_0 representing the goal and start positions. Thus DMPs consist of two fundamental components: a linear second-order attractor, characterized by K and D which act as the spring constant and damping term, and a nonlinear forcing term $f(z)$.

III. FORMULATION

In this section, we will show how to generalize any unicycle path by combining the DMP framework with a Lyapunov-based controller [4]. We will begin by introducing this controller for posture stabilization and then showcase its integration with DMPs to create modified DMPs.

A. Point-to-point motion

First, referring to Fig 1, we establish a system of polar coordinates with respect to a goal frame (X_g, Y_g) , rotated by an angle ψ_g . Then we obtain the kinematic model differentiating in time the model in polar coordinates:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\rho} &= -v \cos(\beta), \\ \dot{\phi} &= v \frac{\sin(\psi)}{\rho}, \\ \dot{\beta} &= v \frac{\sin(\psi)}{\rho} - \omega.\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

Choosing $\bar{v} = v/\rho$, we find a feedback controller considering the following Lyapunov candidate function, and his Lie derivative:

$$V = 1/2(\rho^2 + \phi^2 + \beta^2), \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{V} = -\rho^2 \cos(\beta)\bar{v} - \beta(\omega - (\sin(\beta) + \phi \operatorname{sinc}(\beta))\bar{v}). \quad (6)$$

Now, let's choose inputs to ensure a negative definite \dot{V} as

$$\Gamma_v = v = \rho k_v \cos(\beta), \quad (7)$$

$$\Gamma_\omega = \omega = k_b \beta + k_v (\sin \beta + \phi \operatorname{sinc}(\beta)) \cos(\beta), \quad (8)$$

with k_v and k_b as positive constants.

B. Modified DMPs

The proposed solution below aims to leverage the control strategies mentioned above by integrating them with the DMP approach. First, we define the new DMP as:

$$\tau v = \Gamma_v + \rho_0 f_v(z), \quad (9)$$

$$\tau \omega = \Gamma_\omega + \rho_0 f_\omega(z). \quad (10)$$

With ρ_0 representing the ρ value at $t = 0$. We now proceed to define the desired forcing terms. So, given the demonstrated speeds as v_d and ω_d , we reverse the previous ones:

$$f_{d,v}(z) = \frac{\tau v - \Gamma_v}{\rho_0}, \quad (11)$$

$$f_{d,\omega}(z) = \frac{\tau \omega - \Gamma_\omega}{\rho_0}. \quad (12)$$

IV. SIMULATION

Simulations performed in Matlab shows the generalized trajectory with a new goal chosen as: $x_g = 2.0$, $y_g = -0.5$ and $\psi_g = -\pi/8$. In the plots (Fig 2 and Fig 3), we compare our method with the classic one [2], and most important we show how the latter violate the constraints.

V. CONCLUSION

This work expands upon the DMPs framework for autonomous robot navigation. We have introduced a novel approach for generalizing the trajectory of a unicycle-modeled robot, exploiting a point-to-point Lyapunov controller. As demonstrated in the simulation section, this combination has enabled the development of a versatile formulation capable of addressing the non-holonomic constraints inherent to the unicycle model. However, it is important to acknowledge that this method still has certain limitations, which are currently the focal point of our ongoing work. First, it doesn't perform well when dealing with more complex trajectories, especially after computing the weights. Another one is that it lacks a collision avoidance formulation, which is very useful for this application.

Fig. 2. Plot showing the unicycle trajectories. During the demonstration, we initially commanded the unicycle with a negative velocity and then had it change direction (as indicated by the arrows). The following constants were chosen for the controller: $k_v = 0.5$ and $k_b = 1.3$. Note: for this work, we calculate our DMPs solely based on f_d , without computing weights.

Fig. 3. Three plots showing a comparison between x and y coordinates and the ψ steering angle, followed by a plot evaluating the non-holonomic equation, which should remain zero at all times. Classic DMPs violate the constraints.

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